

Facile green synthesis of gold nanoparticles and its cytotoxic activity against MCF-7 cell line

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Abstract : The façade of nanoscience is the creation and utilization of materials at the nanometer scale, has been a great influence on diagnostics and therapeutics. The notion of green chemistry principle for the synthesis of noble metal nanoparticles is to conquer the problems with the chemical synthesis and hybrid technologies. Present findings demonstrate the biological synthesis of gold nanoparticles using the aqueous rhizome extract of *Alpinia galanga*. The reaction was completed in two minutes. The sizes of newly synthesized gold nanoparticles are ranging from 9 to 36 nm. The newly formed gold nanoparticles were found to be stable. UV-Vis spectrum reveals the SPR λ_{max} at 538 nm. X-Ray diffraction measurement clearly reveals that the newly formed gold nanoparticles are crystalline in nature. It is interesting that the newly synthesized gold nanoparticles corroborated cytotoxic effect in MCF-7 cell lines.

Keywords : *Alpinia galanga*, MCF-7 cells, MTT assay, cell cytotoxicity.

Introduction

Rising awareness towards the biological synthesis of nanomaterials has lead to a yearning to develop nanomedicine. Currently, there has been great interest in the synthesis of nanoparticles with unique physico-chemical features as they discover the applications in areas such as drug delivery¹, biomedical sciences², catalysis³ and electronics⁴. The distinctive features of gold nanoparticles such as comparable size with bioorganic molecules, binding capability to various molecules and optical properties in the visible and NIR regions make them exciting candidates for biological applications⁵. Nanoscience has the potential that can lead to revolutionary breakthrough in the field of cancer therapeutics. Results of the present findings demonstrate anticancer activity of gold nanoparticles synthesized using rhizome of *Alpinia galanga*. Globally, breast cancer is the 5th most common cause of death from cancer in women, and estimated to be responsible for almost 4,60,000 deaths in 2008⁶. The plant *Alpinia galanga* has been widely used in medicine for the treatment of a wide spectrum of disease including, hypoglycaemic⁷, antioxidant⁸ and hypolipidemic activities⁹. Breast cancer (MCF-7) cell lines were subjected for the anticancer investigation using newly synthesized gold nanoparticles.

Materials and methods :

Biosynthesis of gold nanoparticles using Alpinia galanga :

1 mM solution of 100 mL chloroauric acid at concentration of 10^{-3} M prepared by dissolving double distilled water. Five grams of finely powdered rhizome was mixed with 100 mL of deionized water and filtered through Whatman No.1 paper. Different concentration of *Alpinia galanga* extract and chloroauric acid solution (0.5 : 4.5, 1.0 : 4.0, 1.5 : 3.5, 2.0 : 3.0, 2.5 : 2.5) was subjected respectively. The rapid reduction of gold ions to gold nanoparticles was measured using UV-Visible spectrometer.

Characterization of gold nanoparticles :

Aliquots of the reaction solution absorbance were measured using UV-2300 Techcomp spectrometer operated at a resolution of 1 nm. X-Ray diffraction measurements of the newly fabricated gold nanoparticles were carried out on a Siefert X-ray diffractometer operated at a voltage of 30 mA with monochromatic Cu-K α radiation. The morphology of gold nanoparticles was examined by employing Scanning Electron Microscopy (FEI Quanta 200). The studies on morphology and size of gold nanoparticles were carried out by means of Transmission Electron Microscopy (JEOL 3010).

In vitro anticancer studies of synthesized gold nanoparticles :

Cell viability assay :

In brief, the cultured MCF-7 cells (1×10^6 cells/mL) were plated, then the cells were exposed to various concentration of gold nanoparticles (6, 12.5, 25, 50, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) and the cytotoxicity was observed by MTT assay. The inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) of newly synthesized gold nanoparticles was determined from the graph of the number of visible cells against gold nanoparticles concentration¹⁰.

*Morphological investigation of *Alpinia galanga* synthesized gold nanoparticles treated MCF-7 cells :*

MCF-7 cells were cultured in 12 well plates and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h before being treated with gold nanoparticles. Later the cells were treated with 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of gold nanoparticles for 48 h. The cytomorphology was examined using Nikon inverted microscope.

Results and discussion

The aqueous rhizome extract of *Alpinia galanga* was added to the chloroauric acid solution, the biosynthesis reaction completed within two mins and the colour change was observed. The newly synthesized gold nanoparticles using rhizome extract of *Alpinia galanga* showed a strong and broad band at 538 nm, which corresponds to SPR excitation of the gold nanoparticles. XRD spectrum of the newly synthesized gold nanoparticles shows diffraction peaks in the spectrum at 2θ value assigned to (111), (200), (220) and (311) planes respectively. This finding clearly indicates that the newly formed gold nanoparticles are crystalline in nature.

The surface morphology of the newly synthesized gold nanoparticles was studied using Scanning Electron Microscopy. It was observed that the surface of gold nanoparticles synthesized from aqueous rhizome extract of *Alpinia galanga* solution clearly indicates that they are well dispersed (Fig. 1). The shape and size of the gold nanoparticles were determined using High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy. Fig. 2 shows that the gold nanoparticles are dispersed well and mostly in spherical shape with the particle size range from 9–36 nm.

The morphological observations of MCF-7 cells were irregular confluent aggregates with rounded and polygo-

nal cells. The gold nanoparticles treated MCF-7 cells shows condensed nuclei and fragmentation, membrane, blebbing and cell shrinkage are due to reactive oxygen species. The effect of gold nanoparticles concentration on MCF-7 cell viability is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 1. SEM micrograph of *Alpinia galanga* synthesized gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 2. TEM micrograph of *Alpinia galanga* synthesized gold nanoparticles.

Fig. 3. Morphological analysis of MCF-7 cells : (A) Control, (B) IC_{50} and (C) Cytotoxic effects of *Alpinia galanga* mediated gold nanoparticles.

Conclusion

Present investigation discloses biosynthesis and functionalization of gold nanoparticles as anti-breast cancer nanomaterial. The functionalization was achieved neither with conjugation nor by doping of molecule.

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